

Keeping It Full: The Meaning of the Refrigerator for Domestic Consumption and Reproduction in Modern Everyday Life in Turkey

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Abstract

The refrigerator is one of the most significant items of domestic technology products to manage everyday domestic life in the modern world. The refrigerator is not only simply indispensable to preserve food, but also its usage informs us of the ways in which certain cultural meanings, values and emotions are shaped and experienced with regard to domestic reproduction and consumption.

The premise that material objects convey emotions gives reference to emotional aspects of everyday practices conducted by objects. Emotional aspects of practices within everyday realities of people motivate certain dispositions around the objects in use. In terms of family care, the refrigerator serves for the management of a socio-culturally highly valued reproductive function in Turkish domestic life, that is, feeding. I argue that reproduction of domestic life with the help of domestic technology products, concurrently, reproduces the social and cultural values, meanings and emotions that are attributed both to those products and domestic reproduction and consumption. Thus, dispositions around the refrigerator can be regarded as a repository for the perpetuation of those attached values and meanings.

As part of a larger socio-ethnographic study on the use of the refrigerator in Turkey, this paper is about the refrigerator stories that reveal emotional responses of my informants to the degree of abundance of food in their refrigerator with regard to the symbolic aspects of domestic reproduction and consumption. People from different social strata respond differently to that issue. The main concern is to understand the ways in which those emotional responses generate certain dispositions around the refrigerator.

Keywords: refrigerator, domestic consumption and reproduction, emotions, dispositions around the refrigerator.

Introduction

The refrigerator is the ultimate appliance to preserve food in modern everyday life. For the very same reason, it is one of the most essential and commonly used domestic technology products to manage daily domestic life.

The refrigerator is not only simply indispensable to preserve food, but also its usage informs us about certain cultural meanings, values and emotions with regard to domestic consumption and reproduction. In terms of family care, the refrigerator basically serves for the management of a socioculturally highly valued reproductive function in Turkish domestic life, that is feeding. Hence, as an indispensable domestic technology product, its usage

crosscuts different lifestyle understandings experienced within different social layers of the society by different social status groups in Turkey.

As part of a larger socio-ethnographic study on the use of the refrigerator, this paper is about the refrigerator stories that reveal emotional responses of my informants to the amount of the food in their refrigerator. People from different social strata respond differently to that issue. Those emotional responses inform us about both the ways in which practices around the refrigerator and the meaning of the refrigerator are shaped with respect to the sociocultural meanings of domestic consumption and reproduction in modern everyday life in Turkey.

Domestic consumption and reproduction as a cultural process

The premise that material objects convey emotions gives reference to the emotional aspects of everyday practices conducted by objects.

In Turkey, the central issues around the refrigerator are mainly feeding the family and the organization of the food consumption and reproduction practices in terms of the management of the household economy.

Elizabeth B. Silva (2000) shows in her study on the uses of domestic technologies at home that the notions of practice and disposition in terms of care are differentiated and bound together on the basis of the concept of emotional capital. Silva (2000: 2) suggests that “The practice of care refers to the material accomplishment of tasks and activities while the disposition to care refers to the emotional investment in caring.” Referring to Bourdieu’s concept of habitus, Silva (2000: 3) points out that the habitus “defined as a structure of disposition, which predisposes individuals to certain practices (choices and actions), does not give relevance to the emotional aspect of social actions.” Thus, Silva (2000: 4) argues that “In contexts where emotional responses are valued, emotional capital can be said to exist.” Accordingly, Silva’s concept of emotional capital refers to “a capacity to connect involving acts, intentions and sentiments. It refers to moral thinking about personal connections and intimate life, related to the self and to others. It is an essential ingredient for a reflexive self.” (Silva 2000: 4).

The emotional aspects of practices within everyday realities of people motivate certain dispositions around the objects in use. In other words, emotions and emotional investment about practices within the everyday realities of people are contained by the dispositions around the objects in use. Obviously, dispositions motivate certain strategies of practices. Like any other classification category in Bourdiean terms; social, economic, educational and cultural capital [which determine the ways individuals are involved, integrated in a sociocultural system], emotions, contained as emotional capital, can act as one of the markers of distinction between the different forms of class habitus (Silva, 2000). As Deborah Lupton (1998: 2) argues “emotions are phenomena that are shaped, experienced and interpreted through social and cultural processes”.

How do emotions inform us about the ways in which practices around the refrigerator and the meaning of the refrigerator are shaped and experienced with respect to the sociocultural meanings of domestic consumption and reproduction in modern everyday life in Turkey? “Within the home, then, resources are managed, services are performed and some goods may be produced as well as consumed.” (Jackson and Moores 1995: 2) Home is the site of both consumption and reproduction.

That domestic consumption can simply be defined as the purchase of goods by the household for homemaking process has a history as long as the household has ceased to be the locus of economic production and has taken its part in the exchange economy (Putnam 1992). Accordingly, domestic reproduction can be defined by the consumption function of the modern household that the purchased goods are actively combined, reshaped and transformed to produce services like feeding, cleaning, relaxation, leisure (Jackson and Moores 1995). Thus, the modern household is the site of provisioning and economic management (Clarke 2001), which are both temporally and spatially bounded within the house itself in the modern urban context. The refrigerator can be seen, then, within the framework of domestic consumption and reproduction, not just as a simple storage device to preserve food, but also as a resource management device and a monitor of household provisioning which has a significant role for the economic management of the household.

There is a diverse literature that describes the household as a cultural nexus. Domestic consumption and reproduction involve and reveal multidimensional social and cultural processes through the layers of the relations within the household between the family

members, and outside the household between the different households from different class divisions in a given society.

To situate the household within the terms of the moral economy, as Silverstone, Hirsch and Morley (1992: 19) emphasize is “to understand the household as part of a transactional system, dynamically involved in the public world of the production and exchange of commodities and meanings. But that involvement is not a passive one. At stake is the capacity of the household or the family to create and sustain its autonomy and identity (and for individual members to do the same) as an economic, social and cultural unit.”. Thus, while keeping up the daily routine of provisioning, consumption and reproduction within the domestic sphere become engaged with the very exchange system of commodities and meanings, concurrently defining and sustaining the family’s or the household’s identity as a cultural unit. Families across the social strata employ different resources and strategies within the process of consumption and reproduction both at the level of appropriating the material and the meaning. As Silverstone *et al.* (1992: 18) define “The moral economy of the household is therefore both an economy of meanings and a meaningful economy; and in both of its two dimensions it stands in a potentially or actually transformative relationship to the public, objective economy of the exchange of goods and meanings.”.

Within the framework of the household as a moral economy, all the domestic practices and the objects to perform those practices, in turn, are subject to the process of meaning production, which is a socioculturally bounded process in and out of the home. Culturally and emotionally contained dispositions and practices act as markers of distinctions between the different forms of class habitus.

Besides its obvious functional significance for running the daily domestic routines of the household, the refrigerator is conceptualized in this study as a resource management device and as a monitor of the household provisioning. Within the process of sociocultural politics and economy of meanings, the refrigerator acts as a mediator and a monitor of the moral economy of the household. I particularly argue in this study that reproduction of domestic life with the help of domestic technology products, concurrently reproduces the social and cultural values, meanings and emotions that are attributed both to those products and domestic consumption and reproduction. Thus, dispositions around the refrigerator can be regarded as a repository for the perpetuation of those attached values and meanings.

Keeping it full: ‘*I feel uncomfortable when it’s empty...*’

This paper presents ethnographic examples to explore the ways in which emotional responses motivate strategies of use around the refrigerator and generate meanings of the refrigerator, which involve dreamed or desired practices and/or goods, positional definitions within the social strata, values and judgments about the meanings of domestic consumption and reproduction.

This study is part of a larger scale socio-ethnographic research on the use of the refrigerator across the social strata. Since it is an inquiry into the sociocultural significance of the refrigerator to understand how a common modern lifestyle understanding has emerged and developed in Turkish society, the scope of the theoretical and conceptual framework and the range of the ethnographic aspects surpass those of the present study. Due to the extensive variety of the issues about domestic consumption and reproduction related to the refrigerator, and the ethnographically-minded concerns to grasp the whole sociocultural profile of each household, the content of the ethnographic inquiry is not limited with the refrigerator itself.

The ethnography is based on in-depth interviews involving sixty households from six different neighborhoods in Ankara, the capital city of Turkey. The informants are predominantly women, extensively due to their role as homemakers. In rare occasions, husbands participated in the interviews based on the degree to which they felt and regarded themselves as engaged in the household management in general and the issues about the refrigerator in particular.

The ethnographic examples I present here involve households from three different social status groups, namely the lower, middle and upper-middle groups. The lower class households are from the squatter neighborhoods in Ankara.[1] The examples of the middle class households I present here are from a neighborhood situated in the south of Ankara which is known by its typical middle class profile. The examples of the upper-middle class households I employ here are from one of the oldest affluent neighborhoods in Ankara, which has been inhabited by seemingly well off residents with high social, cultural and educational capital.

The narratives of the women I exemplify in this study are based on their emotional responses to the amount of the food in their refrigerator. The women's narratives mainly address their emotional investment into the family care, which has no monetary exchange value, the strong emphasis they make on the significance of hospitality in terms of offering food to their guests and their emotionally driven understandings and judgments about their family's sociocultural status in terms of the level of socioeconomic well-being.

The predominant themes in the narratives of the women I interviewed in the squatter neighborhoods were poverty and privation, and the way they feel as these are reflected into the content of their refrigerator.

Sevim [2] *I would like to buy a bigger refrigerator, a big one! I'm crazy about refrigerators, because it's so important! If it's bigger I can put more food in it. You can put and preserve everything in it! So, you can find anything you need, and prepare anything you want. Just cook! When a guest comes over you can easily prepare anything you want to offer and eat it! Besides, a big refrigerator is necessary for stocking up on food.*

Figen *Then, what does the refrigerator mean for a home in your opinion?*

Sevim *It's one of the members of the family! One that works and produces for the home, I see it that way.*

... I feel very uncomfortable [when it is empty]. I feel as if I'm in hunger, as if there is hunger in this home! Although I'm not very fond of eating a lot, it should definitely be full!

In her narrative Sevim sees the refrigerator almost as a family member in terms of its reproductive values. Earlier in our conversation she talked about how little she always ate all day. Her physical appearance was reflecting that, as she was a very thin woman frequently smoking and drinking tea a lot. Although she states she is not very fond of eating, she feels a strong anxiety of being at the edge of a serious privation when the refrigerator is empty. Although her elder son is married and has a separate home, he and his wife with their one-year-old baby come over to stay in Sevim's house frequently enough to regard that they actually live together. The main reason behind this is to cut back on the heating expenses in winters. The fifty-two-year-old Sevim works as a house cleaner for the last fifteen years. After getting divorced from her husband six years ago, she has become the main provider in the family. She finds it crucial to have a full refrigerator both to feel safe about feeding her family properly and be able to offer proper food to her guests whenever they come over. For these reasons, it is important for her to stock up on food within her refrigerator.

Correspondingly, she was very keen on offering whatever she could to me during our approximately four-hour conversation. The level of abundance in the refrigerator is proportional to its size in her opinion.

Showing a proper and a warm hospitality to guests, especially in terms of offering qualified homemade food is a significant sociocultural norm in Turkish society. The importance and the moral values attributed to hospitality, especially with reference to stocking up on homemade produce in the freezer part of the refrigerator frequently came up in the narratives of the women regardless of their class status, education and whether they have a career outside the home or not.

In the following example, the dynamics of comparison to a seemingly similar but slightly different neighbor and to a considerably different use of the refrigerator pictured in TV advertisements govern the narrative of Fatma, a forty-three-year-old housewife.

***Fatma** When I see those ads in TV, they fill the fridge amply with fresh vegetables, fruits and everything. I don't know, may be there are people who can do that. I don't know... for we cannot do such a thing, you know... If we can go to the farmers' market one week we cannot for the following week; at most once in every two weeks.*

***Figen** How do you feel when your fridge is empty?*

***Fatma** It's a bad thing, one feels really bad. She [pointing her neighbor sitting next to me] lives with her mother-in-law, she can buy anything, her mother-in-law looks after them, it's a nice thing. You know, when a guest comes over you don't feel bad, you can take some stuff from the freezer and heat it up. But every time when a guest comes over I find it very difficult... You know, it's really very important to have a fridge/freezer for poor families like us so that we can put some fresh vegetables and everything in it during summer when everything is cheaper.*

While we were having our conversation with Fatma a neighbor of hers whom I interviewed later, accompanied us and was involved occasionally in our conversation. Later, during the interview with that neighbor, Fatma came over and the neighbor gave her a pack of homemade frozen food from the freezer for her to cook the evening meal.

In the following examples, the narratives of the two middle-class women are rather focused on their concerns of keeping their habit of maintaining a constant order at home.

***Nermin** I've been training myself about that, [to avoid buying food more than she needs] because I wasted a lot of food that way in the past, threw out a lot. I guess it's a habit! Though I feel very uncomfortable when my refrigerator is empty.*

***Figen** Why do you feel uncomfortable about that?*

***Nermin** If you fill it more than you need, you certainly end up throwing some spoiled food away after a while. But seeing the refrigerator empty, then it's against your habits.*

***Figen** How do you feel when it gets empty?*

***Nermin** It's a thing that I never encountered until now. Say, you come home in the evening, you open your refrigerator and do not know what to do for dinner. What would you do?! It gets really more important if you have a child. Especially after having my son, I started feeling an urge to keep my refrigerator always full, almost at the level of stocking. Yet, mine is never as full as mom's!*

...

***Figen** Is your refrigerator always as full as it is now?*

***Nermin** No. It is usually fuller than that actually. Sometimes, I cannot fit everything in I buy, then I put them in the hallway or keep them in the balcony.*

The thirty-eight-year-old Nermin, public relations expert, reveals her way of developing the right strategy against the play of two contradictory forces. One is her disposition to feed her seven-year-old son properly, thus being always precautionary about the right kind of food in the right amount in her refrigerator. Earlier in our conversation, she put a great emphasis on the importance of getting almost scientifically knowledgeable about the healthy way of feeding a child. The other force is to give up the habit of food stocking -which is a common issue that came up frequently in the narratives of middle-class women- both to become a conscious and responsible consumer, and thus differentiate her identity from her mother's who strongly has that habit.

In the following narrative, the concern for being precautionary is more related with the matter of showing proper hospitality as part of an orderly homemaking duty.

***Figen** You say your fridge never gets empty. What does it mean to you?*

***Suzan** I don't like it when it's empty. I feel much more comfortable when it's full, I feel happy then. It makes me happy when I open its door. Although only the two of us left in this house lately, it is still full every time. But I see some food getting spoiled. That's why I am sacrificing my pleasure of keeping the fridge full, lately. I keep less food than I usually do, especially in the fridge part, but I still do the same things to keep the freezer part full.*

...

Husband *I think she feels sort of... as if there is something wrong about her duties as a housewife when the refrigerator is empty.*

Suzan *Yes. I mean, we are used to having guests all the time, we love it. Someone may come over suddenly. For example, my late brother used to come over and bring along like 4-5 friends and say "Oh, my dear, how about just having some delicious food of yours?" So, I'm used to such occasions. Say, if some guests suddenly come over now, I'm totally prepared for that, and comfortably can insist to make them stay for dinner. Because I have everything prepared in the freezer part of my fridge. In a short period of time, even while I'm greeting them, asking them how they're doing, I put the meat in the microwave to thaw it out, and then cook it immediately. See, this gives me confidence and emotional comfort...*

Figen *Does it indicate possibly privation for you when your refrigerator is empty?*

Suzan *No. Because I know myself, I know well about my financial condition. It does not mean privation for me. Main thing is about feeling confident and secure in terms of homemaking.*

Suzan, a sixty-nine-year-old retired chemical engineer, feels happy about a full refrigerator both in terms of sustaining the feeling of vitality in her home and having the pleasure of showing proper hospitality to her guests, especially the suddenly coming over ones. Reflecting a typical middle-class mentality, her concern for keeping the order of proper hospitality corresponds to keeping an orderly household.

In the following two examples from the upper-middle class households, the women's narratives involve rather different concerns in terms of the content and meaning of their emotional responses to the amount of the food in their refrigerator.

Leyla *For I'm a workingwoman, I cook like five different food within one day, and stock them up in my fridge. I preserve them in the freezer part. For the next 2-3 days, I serve them by decorating to create variety.*

Figen *Is your fridge always full?*

Leyla *You know, it's very interesting that a friend of mine came over the other day, she opened it and said "You had nothing in your fridge!". Because during the last month I developed a new strategy about that. I'm not shopping in bulk anymore. I leave my office at around 7:30-8:00 pm and stop by this huge grocery store, buy just whatever I need for the dinner. This takes at least half an hour. When I come home I find three starving boys [including her husband], they say "Where have you been until this hour? We're starving!" Then I get crazy! I do my work, then shop, then carry the stuff all the way home and they're scolding me! So, I decided not to go for shopping after work, only if I have time... Now, the fridge is empty and they feel depressed about that. I'll try this strategy for a while.*

Figen *So, how do 'you' feel when your fridge is empty?*

Leyla *It really touches me, I feel unhappy, devastated.*

Figen *Meaning?*

Leyla *Well, I feel bad if an emergency happens. Plus, my kids are very important to me, I see my cuisine as a motivation for them while they are studying. I always cook or prepare something fun and nutritious for them while they are studying.*

Both the forty-five-year-old Leyla and her husband are dentists, having their own separate offices. Leyla also works occasionally at her husband's office to support him during the peak times. Thus, due to her intense working schedule, the refrigerator is more like a time-management device for her.

Although her friend remarked on the emptiness of her refrigerator, Leyla does not feel anything negative about that and not rate herself and her family in any terms. The change in the level of abundance in her refrigerator reflects the deliberate change she makes in her way of using it, in that it appears as an emotionally driven responsive strategy of negotiating on her role within the family. Putting a great emphasis earlier in our conversation on the skill, quality and sophistication in her cooking beyond the level of necessity, feeding her children reflects her emotional support to them.

On the other hand, a sixty-two-year-old architect Suna sees the refrigerator not more than a bare functional and essential device.

Figen *How do you feel when your fridge is empty and when it is full?*

Suna *I never thought about that. Sometimes it gets so full like packed; then I cannot find even a small space to put anything. For example, I have three fridges in my summerhouse. I use one of them to keep sodas and beverages; one for big fruits like melon, watermelon; and one for the regular food we eat daily. Since it's really very hot there, you need it. I really do not like to deal with so many things about fridges, but I have to anyway.*

...

Figen *So, do you think that it's shopping time and you have to go for shopping when it is empty?*

Suna *Yeah, sort of. Everything finishes up and then we go for shopping. I never buy anything I don't need. I prepare a list, hand it to my husband, then he does it.*

Although Suna has raised two daughters, both now married, she never placed a significance on the refrigerator in terms of either feeding her family or hospitality issues. On the contrary,

she stated that she disliked doing any kind of housework, and thus she has been employing a permanent housekeeper since the beginning of her marriage. Suna does not indicate any sociocultural references based on her emotions about the amount of the food in her refrigerator.

Conclusion

In Turkey, endowed with the sociocultural meanings and values, the refrigerator as a resource management device is a mediator and a monitor of family care, proper accomplishment of household tasks, the quality of hospitality based on the significance of the food as a means of social sharing. Thus, the refrigerator is the monitor and mediator of the moral economy of the household. The obvious gendered orientation in the use of the refrigerator, which is based on homemaking in general and food provisioning in particular, brings forth the inherent gender aspect of the social and economic order of the household, which would be another theoretical axis of argument outside the limited space of this paper.

The above narratives reveal a part of what happens around the refrigerator at home. Those are the emotional aspects of the practices around the refrigerator involving motivated strategies of use; expectations, norms and anxieties about homemaking; feeding the family and the socioculturally highly valued norm of hospitality. Although happening within the physical boundaries of the home, it is a dynamic process always in reference to the sociocultural realm in defining, experiencing and negotiating identities in and out of the home. Based on the idea of the home as a process (Clarke 2001, Miller 2001), the meanings of the material culture at home, mediated through the classification systems like cultural capital, social capital and emotional capital “gives powerful insights into the societies in question.” (Miller 2001: 15). The emotions are inherent quality of our sense of comfort, discomfort, security and anxiety at home in the modern world mediated through the material culture of the home. Thus; “If home is where the heart is, then it is also where it is broken, torn and made whole in the flux of relationships, social and material.” (Miller 2001: 15)

NOTES

[1] Squatter housing in Turkey can be defined as economically marginal housing settlements; in the sense that they are both cheap, and illegal. Those are built as unauthorized within the outskirts of industrially and economically developed cities, literally by the people themselves who migrate from rural to urban areas sustaining the physical and sociocultural aspects of their rural life as reflected in the physical layout of those houses and in their practices of everyday life. Those are poor neighborhoods occupied by the lower classes.

[2] All the informants are called by pseudonyms.

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